

TRAVAILS OF THE FEMALE GENDER IN SELECTED WORKS OF IGBO LITERATURE

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Abstract

In Igbo land, women go through a lot of struggles to cohabit freely with their male counterparts. Women have raised concerns through so many means. This research is targeted at dissecting the struggles of being a woman in selected Igbo literary texts authored by male and female. Researches have been done on related topic but none has selected research literary works hence, the relevance of the study. A descriptive research design was used and Feminist theory, which began with the works of Mary Wollstonecraft (1792), was also used in analyzing literary books. The selected works of Igbo literature show the struggle of the female gender from singlehood to womanhood. She struggles to get married so that society will see her as a responsible person, and this notion has left her vulnerable to any type of maltreatment from men. Then, when they finally make it into a man's home, the struggle to give birth and raise them becomes another mountain to surpass. Thus, this research is beneficial to all and sundry because it will lend a voice in speaking for the female gender and making the male counterpart understand that women have a life to live and they are humans too. It will also help in reshaping the mentality of society concerning women.

Keywords: Female gender, Feminism, Igbo literary authors, Literature, Travail

Introduction

The struggles of the female gender in Igboland seems like a transcended norm because it flows from one generation to another. Authors have used their literary piece to either fight for women or expose how most people feel female gender should be customized. There are some Igbo sayings too that ends up making women feel tensed in the society; “nwata tofee onye mụrụ, a jụwa onye na-alụ” when a child outgrows being in the parents' house, it is expected of her to have a husband. And another says, “di bụ ugwu nwaanyi” being married is the pride of every woman. Njoku (1980) says; “...they saw women's primary role as that of child

bearing to please the husbands". The struggle of a woman is unending from tender to womanhood. The tension of marriage on one side as opined by Agwuna (2004:67) comparing the notion of a man to that of a woman in her work as thus; Uba thought it wise to marry Egodi because she lavishes her father's wealth on him. So, he felt that since she is not like other women who request money from men, then he would marry her despite knowing his parents' stand on the marriage. Ogbalu (1988:98) concurs with the belief that; According to culture, the younger one will not leave before the elder. It is not bad just that it is the people's belief that if the younger marries before the elder, men will start questioning her character.

The pressure from society on the female folks have driven them to lots of things like in the recent times, most young ladies go under the knife spending millions of naira to remake their bodies in order to look attractive and build their self-confidence. Most men love curvy ladies, and most ladies recently feel that if they do not appear curvy, men will not look at them. This act of going under the knife has become a norm, as most celebrities have undergone it, and others outside the industry have taken it up. In fact, ladies have started owning up to it and making the videos of the surgery stages open to social media users to watch. Some death cases have been recorded since the advent of this liposuction. Lambo (2022) shared a story of a lady identified as Crystabel who died after a surgery at the Cynosure Aesthetic Surgery clinics in the Mende area of Maryland, Lagos State. She was reported to have died from complications after the surgery. Ayodele (2022) also wrote about Amelia Pounds, a socialite who died on Friday morning, October 7, 2022, in New Delhi, India, following complications during liposuction surgery.

At the end of the day, she gets married. The issue of childbirth, sex of the baby and getting accepted into her husband's home sets in. as she manages to strive through that stage, she is faced with the responsibility of taking care of the kids and making sure they are not left out amongst their age bracket but immediately the children make it in life, their father takes the trophy as there is an Igbo saying that when the children behaves poorly, they are the replica of their mother but when they progresses in life, they become their father's replica. "Nwa emetaghị ya, ọ buru o yiri nne ya mana nwa mewe nke oma, ọ buru o yiri nna ya". In the marriage, she is more bothered about not just giving birth but having a male child which would solidify her stay in her husband's house and give her access. In as much as they are aware that without a woman there is no procreation but still, Igbos prays so much to have male children who would inherit his father's properties and keep on the family name. Nzeako (1973: v) concurs with the belief.

This is why the society would suggest all manner of things to a couple who has only female children but would lose sleep over one that has male children all through. Ogbalu (1988:24-25) says that when a woman gives birth to only female children, she has no place amongst her husband's kinsmen and her husband will not

be a happy an because after his demise, his brothers and kinsmen will share his properties amongst themselves leaving his daughters with nothing because a female child has no inheritance in her father's house. He went further to say that the natal care given to a woman who gave birth to a male child is different from one who gave birth to a female child because in the case of one who gave birth to a male child, her mother must be there to help out but the one with a female child can be left to see herself through the post-natal period. "otu nwoke ọzọ ka a kọrọ rapuru nwunye ya ka ọ lee onwe ya ọmụgwọ mee ka a siri na ọ bughị oke ihe mere n'ụlọ ya n'ihia na ọ na-amụ so nwaanyi?"

Purpose of Study

The aim of the study is to discuss the struggles of the female gender as depicted in the selected texts by Igbo literary authors which are male and female. This will show how Igbo male gender perceive the female gender and portray them and how the female gender portrays their struggles in a way different from what the opposite sex is unaware of.

Scope

This study is based on selected Igbo literature written by Igbo authors. They include:

Adaeze by Inno

Isi Akwụ Dara n'Ala by Tony Ubesie

Onọdu Ugo by Obidiebube

Nwata Rie Awọ by Goddy Onyekaonwu

Conceptual Framework

Literature is a creative art which is written or orally transmitted. Uzochukwu (1990) said that literature is from a latin word "litera" which means letters. It is a saying or a written artistic work written in an artistic language. Nwadike (1992) opined with the definition of Uzochukwu but says that literature can be explained in two ways; literature as a creative art and literature as a text. As a creative work, it looks at the genres; novel, short stories, drama and poem. As a text for study, it refers to all the text books which aids learning.

Oruchalu (1999) explained that literature is meant to reflect the tradition, custom and belief system of a people which will help in correcting societal ills. He further says that literature plays a vital role in the growth of a community.

Nnyigide (2015:14) sees literature as one's creative output about life, both seen and unseen happenings in the world, real or fiction, the beauty of literature lies in the artistic use of language (figures of speech and figures of expression),

Feminism

International Women's Development Agency (IWDA), a proudly feminist organization, noted that feminism is about respecting diverse women's experiences, identities, knowledge and strengths, and striving to empower all women to realize their full rights. It is about levelling the playing field between genders and ensuring that diverse women and girls have the same opportunities in life as boys and men.

Feminism has so many ideologies to it. Some of which include;

- i. The advocacy of women's rights on the basis of the equality of the sexes.
- ii. The theory of the political, economic and social equality of the sexes.
- iii. The belief that men and women should have equal rights and opportunities.
- iv. The doctrine advocating social, political and all other rights of women equal to those of men.

Feminism at its core is about equality of men and women not "sameness".

Travail

Vocabulary.com states that travail comes from a sinister Latin word; "trepalium" meaning "instrument of torture". It defined travail in so many ways; exerting monumental effort but suffering as you do so or Use of physical or mental energy; hard work.

It went further to explain that; if you had to bust your behind, burn the midnight oil, and shed blood, sweat, and tears to get where you are today, you could say you have endured significant travail. In other words, back-breaking hard mental exertion or physical labour.

Theoretical Framework

The theory used for the study is feminism. According to Ifejirika (2014:64), feminism is a socio-cultural movement which started in the United States of America in the 1920's whose major objectives were not only to create awareness (both for females and males) of the potentials of women as complete human beings. He stretches that feminist critic is interested in the following;

- i. The presentation of female characters in works of art authored by males.
- ii. The presentation of male characters in female authored literary works.
- iii. Attitude of male characters towards female characters.
- iv. The perception of men towards women.

- v. The perception of the position of females in the society prior to the emergence of

Literature Review

There have been related researches to this study which centered around feminism, marginalization of women and their struggles. Thus, these reviews related topics and shows the gap this study fills.

Silas & Enejo (2020) in their paper titled “Disinheritance and Women development in Igboland, Eastern Nigeria: A theological, Ethical Study”, showed the segregation between the male and female folks in the society right from the family. They said the Igbo cultural practices supports or promote disinheritance of daughters, women and widows which seems not to maximally encourage women development physically, intellectually, emotionally, socially and morally. This shows that the struggle of the female gender is unending because she strives so hard to get everything and at the end of the day, she is marginalized within the family she joined in working hard for.

Anagor (2021) in a paper titled; “Mmepe Obodo na Ndu Umunwaanyi” discussed the situation of women before westernization and thus far. It was discovered that women were seen but never heard in Igboland. Their place was in the kitchen and their responsibilities were caring for the husband and children in addition to chores. Society reduced them to a just being without dreams and aspirations. But now, women have gotten voices and many have walked their way to limelight through education.

Anagor (2022) discussed the tradition of the Igbo people that depict the struggles of women in a paper titled; “African Valure, Gender Inequality & Feminism: The Igbo Race”. It was seen that women have been trained in a way to suite men like in the tradition of “iru mgbede”. It is a tradition done for ladies of marriageable age to groom them and their bodies to be selected by men for marriage during the festival “Ipu ebe”. She talked about the saying in Igboland women do not point at a man. Invariably, men can point at a woman but she has no right to do same because she is a woman.

Odinye (2022) discussed the diversity in feminism down to African feminism in her study; “African Feminism: An Overview”. She said that these feminist ideologies define the struggle of the female gender within African cultural milieu with a unique feminist consciousness wrapped in female assertiveness and female bonding.

Okeyika (2023) in “Being A Wife in Ifeka’s *Onye Loro Mkpuru Udara* and Nwaozuzu’s *Mke M Ji Ka: A Comparative Literary Analysis*” says; a wife is believed not to be a whole without the husband and this makes the wife in question undergo a lot of things so as to always maintain the title “wife”. This shows the fact that women pass through phases which are unending down to married life.

Edemadu (2025) agreed to the fact that women have contributed a lot especially in the social and religious aspects of their various families, localities or communities in a paper titled “The Status of Women: Social and Religious Roles of Women in the Pre-Colonial Igbo Society”. While they may not have held formal political titles in the precolonial times, their influence reached far beyond. This shows that women have never been kitchen warmers, they have been working hard to be seen and heard as much as the men.

Okeyika & Orji (2025) selected two drama texts which *Nwaanyi Bu Ihe Ukwu* and *Onodu Ugo* which is one of the texts used in this research to showcase the difficulties of the female gender. in their paper titled; “Female Characters in Obidiebube’s Selected Igbo Plays: The Trauma of Cultural Subjectivity” they asserted that the women in the texts vulnerable and as such were subjected to cultural trauma which is no doubt the reason why they employ the principles of feminism to fight for equal right. This is a clear suggestion of the travails of women in the society as seen in Igbo context.

In summary, there are studies and researches done on related topics and in the selected Igbo literary texts but none has used the covered the topic using the whole selected Igbo texts. Hence, there is need for this study to delve into the topic using the selected Texts in order to discuss how the male authors see the struggles of the female gender and how female authors explains them in their works.

Synopsis and Analysis of the Selected Literary Texts

Adaeze

Nwadike (1998) told a story of a girl, Adaeze, whom Uchechukwu, the father, sees no need to train in school because to him, it is of no use sending a girl child to school. It does not end there; there is another issue of the man not contributing to the upkeep and nurturing of his entire family. He left his fatherly role for his wife, Uzumma, to play, and the woman would stop at nothing in making sure her children become somebody in life. She struggled all through but achieved her aim in life. Page 18 tells of Mr. Uchechukwu’s character towards his household.

Mgbe ọ bụla ọ natara ụgwọ ọnwá ya, ya na nwunye ya na ụmụ
ya adịrị n’okwu. Iwepụta ego nri na-abụ okwu na ụka; ọzọ kwa,
site n’afọ ruo n’afọ, ọ dighị nwa ya ọ na-azụnye uwe. Ma ha

agba ọtọ, ma ha asụ uwe, nke ahụ agbasaghị ya; nsogbu niile a
bụ ihe dịrị nwunye ya ihu etu ọ ga-esi gbaa mbọ

Aside from not taking care of his household, which also includes his wife wellbeing and appearance, he salivates over another woman who is well taken care of by another man, and that was how he started womanizing because he likes beautiful women. His illicit behaviour saps money from his pocket, and that is why he does not have savings, as he spends on his numerous girlfriends, forgetting he has a family to cater to. Page 19 says;

Ọ naghị azurụ onye ụlọ ya akwa, ọ buladi mgbe emume di ka ekeresimesi na ndi ozo, ma yah u umu nwaanyi nwoke ibe ya ebe ha jikechara, juputa na nwaanyi, akpiri etowe ya. Nke a tinyere ya n'ajo omume isoghari umu nwaanyi n'ike na inye ha ego aghara aghara, chefuo na ya tufuchaa ego niile a n'ahu ha, ihe o ketara bu ihoro akwu na nhoru na o mekataghi ka ya buru isi akwu n'ogbe.

In 24, Mrs. Uzumma depicts the struggles of a woman who not only has gone through labour pains in giving birth to her children but is now faced with the task of nurturing them and taking care of all their needs as well as making sure her means of livelihood is sustained. She does all these without taunting her husband or making him feel less of a man.

Ọ bu ihe mere na Uzumma bu ya bu ngwuru ji ulo n'ebe ihe oriri na ihe ya na umu ya na-asu n'ahu di ma, e nweghi mgbe o ji ebu ya isi. Mgbe o bu Uchechukwu na-emeso ya uka, o naghị echetara ya ma ha kowa onu na e wepu ya n'uso, nta aguu egbuola umu ha. Ọ bu eziokwu na o bu ya na-azu ezinaulo ya, ma mgbe o bu iwe gbara Uchechukwu nke na-etinye ya n'ajo omume site n'ifopu nri e sinyere n'oku, Uzumma anaghi agba lipara lipara iji gosi na o bu ya kara keta oke n'ikpa nri. (pg. 25)

The writer talked about one reason why a female child is not been trained simply because of a case of another person which is unverifiable. Most men forget that no one has monopoly of being prodigal; it all depends on the individual. When it comes to a woman, society does not waste time in deciding over her matter but when it has to do with the male gender, the reverse is the case.

A koru akuko banyere otu nwa agboghọ aha ya bu Ndiokwere onye nne na nna ya zuchara na koleji ka o siri la andi muru ya n'iyi site n'igbakwuru otu nwoke. Mgbe ndi mmadu jiri juwa ihe mere ede jiri bee nwii, ihe a si o kwuru bu na ndi muru ya

enyeghị ya ohere ka ọ lụọ onye masịrị ya n'obi. N'ihị nke a, mgbe ha manyekatarara ya ka ọ lụọ onye ihe ya na-adighị ya mma, ya agbapụ gakwuru nwoke ahụ, onye na-emeghị omenala ọ bụla n'isi ya. Nke a mere ka Uchechukwu jụwapụ isi na Adaeze ga-eje akwụkwọ. O kwuru na kama nwamkpi ya ga-efu, ya eree ya mgbe ọ na-agbanbeghị afọ.

When it comes to a woman, the society gets in her way especially in matters concerning her dream and the choices she makes. A man feels it is wrong for a woman to turn their proposals down. But when she does, they see it as a blow to their ego and most of them would go out of their way to pay back. The society wants her to settle down and have a man in her life but immediately she thinks otherwise, it becomes a problem. So is the case with Adaeze who fell love with Nnanna who happens to be Ibedinjo's friend and decided to settle down with him not until she went to NYSC and discovered her calling into the Roman Catholic sisterhood. She decided to pursue her new found calling and her fiancé who could not take the heartbreak confided in his friend Ibedinjo not knowing he has a hidden agenda. He advised his friend Nnanna to take revenge and spill Adaeze's blood. After much persuasion, Nnanna agreed but as God may have it, their plans did not work out well. Page 131 revealed the desire of Adaeze to become a reverend sister and disengage her marriage plans with Nnanna.

...Nnanna, uche m esila n'ihe gbasara ilu di puo. Obi m anakwerela na aga m echi sista. Akwukwo agbara Nnanna ara. O wee kosara otu enyi ya nwoke aha ya bu Ibedinjo.

Ibedinjo kwuru na ọ buru ya ka e mere ihe mgbawaobi di etu a na ya agaghi ahapu onye ahụ ka ọ noro ndu na-eri ji na ede. Ọ gwara Nnanna na ihe ọ ga-eme bu igwo ogwu, nke ga-eme Adaeze odi ndu onwu ka mma; onọ n'ala ahụ egbe.

Ibedinjo displayed his animosity over Adaeze who turned his relationship offer down in the university by advising Nnanna wrongly so as to use him to revenge Adaeze because he saw her decision as an insult to him. Page 133 has this to say;

... Iwe Ibedinjo n'ebe Adaeze no bu na mgbe ha no na yunivasiti, ọ gakwuru ya ugboro ugboro ka ha mee enyi ma mgbe ọ bula ọ gara, Adaeze agbaa ya igbe. Ugbu a, ọ chorọ isi n'aka onye ozọ nugwata ihe mkpari a ọ natara.

This portrays the essence of feminism and what it stands for. Both genders have the right to make their choices either in career or who becomes their partner in life. A woman should not be caused pain because of the choices she makes because both genders are equal before the law.

Isi Akwụ Dara N'Ala

The prose told a story about a young lady who has done well for herself having gone through her academics and gotten a job. She is fulfilled at least she can earn to take care of herself and be useful to both herself and her family because the society frowns at a jobless lady especially when through with schooling. They would say it is good for a woman to have something doing because men of these days would always go for a woman with handiwork or a job. Ubesie (1973:1) says;

“The na-atọ Ada uto ugbu a abughị maka ugwo a na-akwu ya n’oru o nwetara oheru. Ebe obi anuri ya kariri bu na ibe ya teta ura n’utu puwa, o soro ha puwa. Ha lotawa, o soro ha lotawa”.

The character Ada has two things bothering her; getting a job and getting married. This shows the phases of life for every lady after school. She is expected to get a job as a man so as to take care of herself, assist her family and be legible to be married. Secondly, Ada is bothered about getting married as seen in page 1;

“O di ihe abuo chere Ada n’ihu n’oge mbu. Nke mbu bu inweta oru. Nke abuo bu inweta ezigbo nwoke ga-alu ya”.

It further shows the problems of wrong choice in marriage where the Igbos frown at a woman who leaves the husband’s house no matter the condition because to them, living and dying, she has to make her marriage work out for her which is why most ladies are scared to get married because once you are in, no going back. Page 1 has this to say;

“Onye nweta oru, o buru na oru ahụ adighi ya mma, o chorọ oru ozo. A gaghị agbara ya asiri. a gaghị akoro ya ogologo akuko. Okwu na uka adighi ya. Ma onye jee di, o di mma, o di njo, ila azu adighi ya. Onye si be di ya gbaa oso, o nweghi mgbe o ji abu ezi ihe. O masi ya buru di nwaanyi ahụ na-emegbu ya ndi mmadu adighi ele onye obula si na be di ya laa be nna ya ezigbo anya. Ma, iga di bu ahia akpa; a naghị ahụ ihe di ya n’ime anya, ruo mgbe onye ahụ zuru ya ruru be ya, toghere akpa o zutara. Nke a mere na Ada na-ario chi ya ario na-asị ya jiri aka ya chonye ya onye ga-abu nke ya. Iga di abughị ime enyi, ebe o na-abu ubochi o dighikw andi na-eme enyi mma, onye obula achoro onye ozo”

Then again, her joy seems incomplete because she is not married. She does anything and everything within her power to get a man to herself but all to no avail. At a point, the joy of getting a job left her because the stage where she is now is the stage of getting married so, she is not happy that events have not been favorable to her. Ubesie (1973:2) says;

“Ma ọ dila ọnwa isii Ada malitere ọrụ. Ọ dighi onye na-ajụ ya ma ọ kpọwara akpọwa, ma ọ na-ere ere. Obi adighi ya mma. Ọ nọkatara, o jee n’ugegbe na-ele onwe ya ka ọ mara ma ọ jọrọ njọ nke ukwu nke mere na ọmụ nwoke anaghị ele ya ezigbo anya. Ọ nọrọ oge ọfọdụ, ihu ya agbarọọ ka mmiri ruru n’igwe. Iwe na-eju ya obi nke bụ na ọ na-anọrọ n’otu akụkụ na-eche otu n’ime ọmụnne ya ga-agwa ya okwu ka o jiri onye ahụ zee iwe di ya n’obi”

As she adds a year to her age, she began to lose her patience as she uses her income in beautifying herself but after a while when she was not able to attract or keep a man to herself, she lost interest in taking care of herself. Page 2 shows that;

“Ọnwa abụla gafere, Ada ejiri otu ọnwa kari afo ole ọ gbara n’ọnwa gara aga. Ego niile a na-akwụ ya n’ugwo ọnwa bụ maka iji chọọ onwe ya mma. Ma, ebe ọ bụ na ọ dighi nwoke na-eghe ya ezigbo ọrụ, ma ya fọdụ ikwuwe okwu ilu ya, ọ na-adị Ada ka ego niile ọ na-emefu wee na-achọ onwe yam ma bụ ihe lara n’iyi”

This also shows that directly or indirectly, it has been input into the brain of a woman that at a certain age she should leave her parents’ house and get married. It also shows that most beautification women do is to attract or impress men not necessarily because they love it. The author shows that there are events that cause most ladies to be desperate to settle down. One of which is the character of her friends or people around her, as seen in the case of Ada, whose female age mates and colleagues does would always be heard by her discussing their husbands, not putting into consideration the emotional and psychological effect it has on one of them who is still single as in the case of Ada. Page has this to say;

“Ndị ọgbọ ya niile ya na ha na-arukọ ọrụ aluola di. Naanị Ada bụ onye na-alubeghi di. Ha niile nọkọọ ọrụ, ihe ha na-akọ bụ, “di m wee si m, di m wee mee nke a”. Ma, gini ka Ada nwere ikoro ha? O nweghi di, o nweghi enyi. Ha kowa udi akuko a, o jiri nwayo bilie, puoro ha. Ọ bughị ha makariri Ada na mma, ọ bụ onye chi ojojọ ka mmiri na-afa n’eze”

The situation Ada finds herself in and the need to get married took a serious toll on her psychologically and emotionally as she becomes emotionally porous. She also begins to assume that immediately a man shows a little care towards her it shows he wants something serious with her not knowing that assumption kills. That was her case with a character named Obiora. He took advantage of Ada’s emotional fragility and began to lead her on to the extent of visiting her home not until she wanted him to define the nature of their relationship that was when he made it

known to her that he is married with children. Ada was shattered and heartbroken because she has already fallen in love with him. Page 6 says:

“Otu mgbede, Ada nọ ba be ya na-ezu ike. Okpomoku kariiri akari. Akupe Ada ji eku onwe ya enyeghi aka. Ada wee bilie je mata akwa ya, kuru mmiri jewe isa ahụ. Ebe ọ nọ na-asa ahụ, ọ nuru ka mmadu nọ n’ime ulo be ya na-agu egwu udi egwu a na be Ada. Ada wee mara nke oma na ọ bu Obiora na-eche ya n’ime ulo be ya. O wee saa ahụ ngwa ngwa mara akwa ya ngwa ngwa, puta.

Ka ọ na-azobata ukwu n’onu ulo ya, Obiora noro n’oche ọ nọ tie mkpu si Ada, “nne i maara uma na-asa ahụ n’ihi na chi gi kere gi mma site na mbu”. Obi toro Ada utọ nke ukwu nke bu na ọ bira buru oche ya nodewe Obiora. Ha abuo wee malite kowa udi akuko mmadu abuo huru onwe ha n’anya na-ako.

Naani ihe Obiora na-agwa Ada bu etu ya siri hu ya n’anya n aka Ada si maa mma nke ukwu. Ada wee si ya, ebe ọ bu na i huru m n’anya n’udi a i na-ekwu, ọ di gi ka o nwere ihe ga-egbochiri anyi abuo ilu di na nwunye?

...Obiora wee si Ada; aluola m nwaanyi, muta otutu umu. Abuo n’ime ha amalitela jewe akwukwo.

Anyia Ada ghe oghe ma Ada anaghi ahụ uzọ. Nti ya ghe oghe ma Ada anaghi anu ihe. Ọ saghere onu na-ekwu otutu ihe otu mgbe. Ma, n’ime ihe niile ọ na-ekwu, ọ dighi nke nwere isi.

This also shows how the writer depicted the woman figure as being a gender under the mercy of a man and a desperate being who cannot build happiness within her without a man in her life. Then he made a man a mini god who to a woman who can do anything and get away with it. This is one character feminist movement go against stating, all gender is equal and none should take advantage of each other by any means.

Onodu Ugo

Obidiebube (2006) talked about the struggles of a single lady whom not out of her own tuition refused to marry but because the society felt she is too educated and smart to be loyal to a man, which is just a mere assumption. So, because of this assumption, her suitor’s mind was poisoned against her. This shows how society sees a lady who is on top of her career in life. They believe she is not a wife material because they afraid that she is too smart and may not tolerate any form of maltreatment. Page 55 revealed this in a conversation between Mr. Ojukwu whom

the son wants to marry Ngozi and Mr. Onwuka a friend of his whom he has gone to enquire the character of the in-law to be from.

Onwuka: O nwere ihe nwa m huru n'Ugwueke m were si ka m si n'aka gi mara ma o bukwa anu oriri. O nwere akwu chara n'Ugwueke

Ojukwu: N'ulo onye ka o huru akwu o bu?

Onwuka: O bu n'ulo Okonkwo Mmaduka Ngodo Ugwueke. O bu ada ya nwaanyi bu Ngozi guchara akwukwo na-aru oru na Legos ka Chinedu si na ya ga-alu, m were bia ka e mee ya ka e si eme yaa maka na ajughuaju were rie na-eweta ariaghi aria anwu.

Ojukwu: I si na o bu onye? Ngozi? Chinedu nwa gi o na-ezukwara onwe ya ndu? Nwata nwaanyi riwara anya ka Ngozi ka nwa gi choru ilu. Nke mbu bu na Ngozi ga-atu Chinedu; ozo, o guru oke akwukwo, o bu akada. Ozo, o jiri ihe gbasatara egwuregwu gaa otutu ebe. Gwa nwa gi puta na mmadu anaghi anyu nsi ebe ahija ka ya ogo. Udele buru anu oriri, ndi mbu aka erielia ya

The society especially the male gender's fear about a career woman blinds their eyes to the personality of the lady and the family at large. It is clearly seen that in the case of the character Ngozi, the critiques mentioned that the family is good and has no questionable character it is just that the lady has made it in her career.

Osodieme: Adi ama ama, nne na nna ya bu ezigbo mmadu. Ezinaulo ha bu

ezigbo ezinaulo kama na nwa ha riwara anya dika nna anyi kwuru. Mmadu anaghi akpachara anya koro agbara ghaa onwe ya n'ahu.

It was clearly shown that one of the things held against Ngozi is the fact that she is older than Chinedu which to them is not right for a man to marry a lady who is older than him. Whereas, when it has to do with a man, no matter his age, people would not question his decision in marrying a younger fellow. It is also seen that this is why some ladies are single because no one tells the heart whom to love and love knows no age barrier but the society keeps the age record and would file it out against a woman in due time. So, a woman loves with her eyes open so as to fall in love with the requirements stated by the society.

“...Nke mbu bu na Ngozi ga-atu Chinedu”

The author equally showed the notion of many when they see a successful lady still single. They feel that whatever kept a lady to some certain time and age without being married is a sign that something is wrong with her because if not, she would have been married forgetting that the African culture has made it in a way that it is solely in the hands of a man to ask a woman out and propose. No matter how a woman feels about a man, she has to keep up her self-esteem and wait for him to make the first move. Otherwise, some will term her a “desperado” or a loose lady with an unquestionable family upbringing.

“Udele buru anu oriri, ndi mbu aka erielaya”

The age of a woman is not measured same as a man and as Ngozi saw that age was not on her side, she decided to adopt a female child who would look after her at old age and keep her name because she already made a name for herself. Her brother saw it as a weird decision and fought tooth and nail to make sure she does not succeed with her plans. When finally, Ngozi succeeded in adopting the child and had health issues which led to her demise, her brother Obiora whom she laid down her life for at her early stage in life to make him financially stable fought against her adopted daughter to inherit his sister’s properties. (Pg.87-88)

Obiora: Ngozi, onye di ihe a? Ya bu na agwachaala m gi okwu i kachie nti mee ihe bu uche gi. Akowaara m gi na umu m bu umu gi, gi were anyi mere ihe masiri gi mana i nughu ya. Ugbu a, gi bu isi ekotala ebu mara amara na isi kote ebu o gbaa ya. Nwaanyi anaghi ebichi obi n’ala Igbo mana i chorọ ibichi obi ugbu a. ahụ ga-adikwa gi ka onye na-ebichi obi.

Ngozi: Obi, kedụ ihe i jiri lechaa anya bja na be m inye m mkpari? Kedụ ihe mu naa gi na-azọ? O bu nkwu ka o bu ukwa? Obi i na-ekwu okwu ya ka bukwa nke gi. Ala ebe a m ruru ulo bu ala m jiri ego m zuo. Nwa m kpotara bu nwa nwaanyi iji gosi gi n’ezie na enweghi m ebumnobi ozọ kariya ka m nwee onye ga-ele m anya ugbu a m na-aka nka.

Obiora: Ihe ndi ahụ agbasaghi m. Ihe m na-eme ka i mata bu na ana m enye gi otu onwa ka i buru ebeke buchighaa azu ebe i butere .

Obiora categorically told the sister to return the child she adopted because women don not inherit anything in their father’s house all because he is interested in taking over the sister’s wealth. He forgot that the properties owned by the sister was not situated in their father’s compound rather, she acquired a land and built them which is not against the Igbo tradition.

The author being a woman used her book to explain the ordeals of women be it married or single. It shows the burden women carry in making sure their father's house is stabilized. It also shows that some men are terrified when a woman is doing so well for herself, because they feel she will not be submissive. When she eventually decides to adopt a child so as to have who will look after her at old age, it becomes an issue for the family members who are waiting for her to live and dies so that they can enjoy her wealth.

This is what feminism is speaking up against. Women are human beings and should exist as such. Their lives and decisions should not be centered around a man, and men should allow them breathe freely. Every gender should be treated equally, irrespective.

Findings

The study showed that women are mostly berated for any perceived bad character which most of them were committed with men but as the saying; men are men, they are left aside only for the women to be bashed just like in the text *Isi Akwu Dara n'Ala*. The character Ada was portrayed as a desperate person in many situations like; when she was ready to settle down, she was portrayed as one who was forcing herself on men because the society was pressurizing her just because there is an age tag for any lady to settle down so, in order to meet up to that, some tend to desperately search for a man. When things went bad for the family after she got married because of war, the author showed that she slept with the powers that be just to get her business secured.

Women are sexualized in the society, hence the saying; "use what you have and get what you want". This was exactly the case of the character Chinyere in *Okwe Agbaala*. In the case of Adaeze in *Adaeze* took advantage of so many girls in the text and got some pregnant without been sued instead, he paid their dowry just to have right over the unborn kids yet he lived with none.

It is also seen that a woman has limited rights even to decide what she wants for herself because men feel it is their right to decide for a woman as seen in the text *Onody Ugo*. Ngozi, who was not married because of issues that are beyond her control decided to adopt and the brother felt it is wrong despite knowing she is financially capable of grooming a child.

Lastly, marriage seems to be the ultimate for any girl child as far as the parents and society is concerned. The hope of the parents is that the in-law will care for them hence, it is not to be heard that a woman takes the decision to be single as in in the case of Adaeze in *Adaeze*.

The study has shown clearly that being a woman is a struggle to survive in a world with men because a lot is expected from a woman and there is a way the society has shaped the female gender to appear.

Recommendations

There are few recommendations which are as follows;

1. A girl child should be trained in a way that she can uphold her honor and pursue her dreams.
2. The female gender should be given same space to compete with the male gender and should not be relegated to the background.
3. The society should change their notion that once a woman is independent then, she cannot make a good wife or be loyal to a man
4. Society should be devoid of pressurizing the female gender in any way; either into feeling less of a being, pegging her dreams to a certain level just to please the society or getting married because at the end of the day, they will live by any choice they make for themselves be it good or bad.
5. Women should speak out when they are marginalized in sharing the wealth of their fathers because there is a law that states that women can inherit their father's properties too.

Conclusion

The study has shown that the female gender passes through stages of struggle in their lifetime. They struggle to be themselves and discover who they are from a younger stage because they are nurtured to be a mother and as such, they waddle in between their age and that of a mother figure. As they pursue their dreams, they work extra hard to be accorded same respect a man is given in the society as a human being because some will always never agree to the fact that a woman can handle tough positions better just as in the case of Nigeria where some certain positions are kept exclusively for men.

The research has shown from the selected works of Igbo literary works that women are fixed in a tight position in the society right from teenage age to womanhood ranging from the way she is supposed to live her life down to the decisions she makes for herself in her life to when she is of age to settle down. As the woman works to be independent, she has the society waiting anxiously for her to be married because as the Igbo saying goes, "husband is the pride of every woman". So, without that, she is seen as an unfulfilled person. If she is well educated and independent, she becomes a terror as most men see her as a trait, as someone who would not be loyal to them. In all, it is proven that women pass through a lot to be where they are and be who they are.

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